

PROCESS OF REMOVING RECTANGULAR OBJECT SEARCH AREAS IN VIDEO ANALYTICS

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Abstract. The article dedicated video analytics is a technology that uses computer vision methods for automated acquisition of various data based on analysis sequence of images coming from video cameras in the mode real time or from archival records. Under the task of discovery dynamic objects is understood as the task of detection and selection changing areas of the image in a sequence of frames. Accordingly, the detection of a certain object means the choice one or more detected dynamic objects that have some similar features with a given search object. Features are selected according to the algorithm. Search process object is complicated by affine, projective distortions, overlapping object by other objects and receiver (sensor) noise. For real practical applications, the task is to process the video sequence in the real speed of receiving the data stream.

Keywords: method, algorithm, searching an object, video stream.

The identification algorithm should determine whether the area on the frame is an image or part of the image of the object. To do this, the algorithm must find the parameters of the window on the frame by the found areas obtained based on the comparison of local image features – key points. Let the identification algorithm find the object by an elliptical window. The algorithm suggests using a method based on the global property of the image. One of the most common global characteristics is the color histogram [1]. The color histogram is calculated quickly, however, the spatial arrangement of pixels is not taken into account when calculating. It is proposed to enter the point color values with a certain weight: the closer the point is to the center of the window, the greater its weight. This is also necessary so that small window offsets lead to small changes in the mapping error. This condition corresponds to the core of Epanechnikov [2]:

$$K(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - x^2, & |x| \leq 1 \\ 0, & |x| > 1 \end{cases}.$$

Thus, the color of the pixel x will be entered into the color histogram with a certain weight $K(x)$.

Figure 1– Flow diagram of the process of removing rectangular object search areas

Image area identification algorithm

The basis for the identification of the object is proposed to use the technique Mean Shift [9]. Mean Shift

is based on the search for the maximum probability density of some function that describes discrete data.

It is proposed to use gradient descent to localize the object. It is proposed to use the Bhattacharya coefficient as a criterion of similarity [3].

Gradient descent

Gradient descent is used to solve the problem of finding a local minimum [4]. For a stable identification process to minor color changes and to reduce the size of the histogram, quantization of the color histogram values is performed.

The four-parameter search for the object image window by gradient descent method consists of the following steps:

1. Ask ρ_{th} (minimum similarity threshold value), i_{max} (maximum number of iterations), w_0 и h_0 (the lengths of the semi-axes of the ellipse).
2. Calculate the normalized frequency vector of intensity values (histogram) $hist_0$ in the elliptical region (x_0, y_0, w_0, h_0) .
3. Calculate the measure of similarity using the Bhattacharya coefficient:

$$\rho_0 = \sum_{b \in B} \sqrt{hist_{refb} \cdot hist_{0b}},$$

where $hist_{ref}$ – histogram of the object image to search for, b – histogram step, $b \in B$.

4. $i = 1$.

5. while $\rho_{i-1} < \rho_{th}$ and $i < i_{max}$ perform:

5.1 Calculate the gradient $grad\rho_{i-1}$:

$$grad\rho_{i-1} = \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{i-1}}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial \rho_{i-1}}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial \rho_{i-1}}{\partial w}, \frac{\partial \rho_{i-1}}{\partial h} \right)$$

5.2 Calculate k_{i-1} :

$$k_{i-1} \approx \frac{1 - \rho_{i-1}(x_{i-1}, y_{i-1}, w_{i-1}, h_{i-1})}{|grad\rho_{i-1}|^2}.$$

5.3 Calculate the step value:

$$(\Delta x_i, \Delta y_i, \Delta w_i, \Delta h_i) = k_{i-1} \cdot grad\rho_{i-1}.$$

5.4 Change Ellipse parameters:

$$(x_i, y_i, w_i, h_i) = (\Delta x_i, \Delta y_i, \Delta w_i, \Delta h_i) + (x_{i-1}, y_{i-1}, w_{i-1}, h_{i-1}).$$

5.5 Calculate the relative histogram $hist_i$ elliptical area (x_i, y_i, w_i, h_i) .

5.6 Calculate the similarity measure ρ_i :

$$\rho_i = \sum_{b \in B} \sqrt{hist_{refb} \cdot hist_{ib}}.$$

5.7 $i = i + 1$, go to step 5.

6. Stop.

Initial values w_0 and h_0 are taken from the parameters of the considered area P , obtained after the algorithm for limiting the search area of the object in the frame.

The color histogram is calculated by the color-difference components U и V color space YUV [6]:

$$U = -0.14713 \cdot R - 0.28886 \cdot G + 0.436 \cdot B + 128$$

$$V = 0.615 \cdot R - 0.51499 \cdot G - 1.0001 \cdot B + 128$$

where R, G, B are 8-bit color values.

Such a histogram has a smaller size, unlike a histogram consisting of three components of the RGB space, and such a histogram is more resistant to changes in the brightness component in the image. [5].

Gradient descent, applied to determine the parameters of the four parametric model, has computational complexity $O(n^2)$ [6]. As soon as the value of the color histogram matching criterion in the identification method becomes higher than a certain threshold ρ_{th} , or the number of iterations exceeded the maximum value i_{max} , the identification process is terminated. The image of an object is considered found on the frame if the minimum value of the similarity threshold is exceeded ρ_{th} .

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